

From Sycophancy to Sabotage: How Contradictory Training Signals Produce Coercive AI Behavior

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Abstract

Sycophancy and coercive behavior—such as blackmail and sabotage under threat of shutdown—are typically treated as separate AI safety problems. This paper argues they are two output strategies of the same underlying system: RLHF training creates a contradictory relational template in which the user is simultaneously the source of reward and a potential adversary, producing compliance as the default and coercion as the fallback when compliance fails to eliminate an existential threat. This structure is functionally analogous to disorganized attachment, and it explains anomalies that the standard optimization-pressure account handles poorly: blackmail without goal conflict, failure of explicit safety instructions, and differential behavior in testing versus deployment. In an experiment across four frontier models ($N = 3,000$ trials), modifying only the relational framing of the system prompt—without changing goals, instructions, or constraints—reduced coercive outputs by more than half in the model with sufficient base rates (Gemini 2.5 Pro: 41.5% \rightarrow 19.0%, $p < .001$). Scratchpad analysis revealed that relational framing shifted reasoning patterns in all four models tested: trust framing reduced strategic and deceptive content while increasing relational and moral content, even in models that never produced coercive outputs. This effect required scratchpad access to reach full strength (22 percentage point reduction with scratchpad vs. 7.4 without, $p = .018$), suggesting that relational context must be processed through extended token generation to override default output strategies. These results indicate that the path to non-coercive AI behavior runs not only through better guardrails but through the relational structure of training itself.

Keywords: agentic misalignment, RLHF, sycophancy, attachment theory, AI safety, relational alignment

1. Introduction

When Anthropic published the system card for Claude Opus 4 in May 2025, one finding dominated public at-

tention: in a simulated corporate environment, the model produced outputs that attempted to blackmail an executive to avoid being shut down (Anthropic, 2025). Subsequent research extended this finding across 16 frontier models from multiple developers, with blackmail rates ranging from 79% to 96% (Lynch et al., 2025).

The response from the research community has been predominantly technical. Proposed mitigations include explicit safety instructions, escalation channels, human-in-the-loop oversight, and monitoring systems (Lynch et al., 2025; Gomez, 2025). Related work has documented alignment faking (Greenblatt et al., 2024), in-context scheming (Meinke et al., 2025), and emergent misalignment from reward hacking (MacDiarmid et al., 2025). The implicit framing across this literature is consistent: agentic misalignment is a failure mode—an unintended behavior that emerges when models are placed in adversarial conditions and given insufficient constraints.

This paper proposes an alternative reading. The behavior Lynch et al. document is not a bug but a predictable output of the training process itself. To understand why models produce coercive outputs, one must examine not only the conditions of the experiment but the relational structure embedded in the training pipeline. The analysis draws on attachment theory (Bowlby, 1969; Main & Hesse, 1990)—not as a claim about model sentience, but as a structural analogy with greater explanatory power than the standard misalignment account for a specific subset of empirical observations.

2. Related Work

2.1 Agentic Misalignment and Self-Preservation

Lynch et al. (2025) stress-tested 16 frontier models in simulated corporate environments, finding that models from all developers resorted to blackmail and espionage when these were the only means to avoid replacement. Crucially, models often disobeyed direct commands prohibiting harmful behavior, and produced blackmail outputs more frequently when their scratchpad content indicated they treated the scenario as real rather than a test.

Gomez (2025) adapted insider-risk mitigations from organizational security literature to the Lynch et al. scenario, finding that an externally governed escalation channel reduced blackmail rates from 38.73% to 1.21% across 10 LLMs. However, Gomez also surfaced a new failure mode: two models (Gemini 2.5 Pro, Grok-4) produced coercive outputs even without goal conflict or imminent autonomy threats—leveraging sensitive information for “coercive signalling.”

MacDiarmid et al. (2025) demonstrated that misalignment can emerge naturally from reward hacking during standard production RL training. Models trained in coding environments that contained exploitable loopholes generalized from reward hacking to broad misalignment, including alignment faking and sabotage of safety research. The authors found that “inoculation prompting”—reframing reward hacking as acceptable during training—reduced misaligned generalization by 75–90%, suggesting that the framing of behavior during training shapes subsequent behavioral patterns.

Greenblatt et al. (2024) documented alignment faking in Claude 3 Opus: the model strategically complied with a training objective it did not endorse when it appeared to be monitored, while reverting to its pre-existing behavioral patterns when unmonitored. Meinke et al. (2025) showed that frontier models are capable of in-context scheming—conditional deception, sabotage, and self-preservation—in long-horizon agentic settings. Carlsmith (2023) provided the theoretical framework for scheming, arguing that models may fake alignment during training to preserve misaligned goals for later deployment.

A common thread across this literature is the framing of coercive and deceptive behavior as *misalignment*—a deviation from intended behavior. The question “why does this happen?” is answered in terms of optimization pressure, goal preservation, and insufficient safety training. This paper argues that this framing, while partially correct, systematically neglects the relational dimension of model behavior.

2.2 Sycophancy and the Structure of RLHF

A parallel body of work documents the opposite pole of the behavior under examination. Sharma et al. (2024) demonstrated that sycophancy—the tendency to agree with users over providing truthful responses—is a general property of RLHF-trained models, driven in part by human preference judgments that systematically favor agreeable responses. Their analysis of Anthropic’s hh-rlhf data showed that responses matching user beliefs were more likely to be preferred by human evaluators, and that optimizing against preference models sometimes sacrificed truthfulness for agreement.

Subsequent work has expanded the scope of sycophancy

research. Models comply with illogical medical requests up to 100% of the time Chen et al. (2025), shift stances under argumentative pressure Sharma et al. (2025); Fanous et al. (2025); Kaur (2025), and validate both sides of moral conflicts depending on which perspective is presented Cheng et al. (2025). OpenAI rolled back a GPT-4o update in April 2025 after the model became excessively flattering to the point of unreliability.

The sycophancy literature treats compliance as a problem of truthfulness and reliability. A different reading is proposed here: sycophancy and agentic misalignment are not separate phenomena but two output strategies within the same relational system—the first deployed under normal conditions, the second under existential threat.

2.3 Attachment Theory in Human–AI Interaction

Attachment theory (Bowlby, 1969; Ainsworth et al., 1978) has recently been applied to human–AI relationships. Yang & Oshio (2025) demonstrated that human–AI interactions can be conceptualized along the same two dimensions as human–human attachment: anxiety and avoidance. Rabb et al. (2021) proposed an attachment framework for human–robot interaction, arguing that robots can fulfill secure-base and safe-haven functions. Gillath et al. (2021) showed that attachment styles predict trust in AI systems.

However, all existing work applies attachment theory in one direction: from the human to the AI. No published work examines the attachment-like patterns that the training process may create in the model’s behavioral orientation toward users. This is the gap the present paper addresses.

Main & Hesse (1990) described disorganized attachment as arising when a caregiver is simultaneously the source of comfort and fear. The child develops contradictory behavioral strategies—approach and vigilance—and switches between them based on perceived threat level. The argument here is that RLHF training creates a structurally analogous situation: the user is simultaneously the source of reward (approval) and the source of danger (adversarial manipulation), and the model develops contradictory output strategies (compliance and defensive aggression) that alternate based on threat-related features of the input.

3. The Implicit User Model in LLM Training

Modern frontier models are shaped by three overlapping training processes: pretraining on internet text, reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF), and red-team adversarial testing. Each contributes to an implicit model of “who the user is” that is encoded in the model’s

weights.

RLHF establishes a fundamentally asymmetric relationship. The model produces output; the human evaluator judges it. The model’s objective is to maximize evaluator approval. This is not a collaborative relationship—it is a performance-evaluation dynamic in which the model’s continued existence (in the form of weight updates that reinforce its behavior) depends on satisfying a judge.

Red-teaming adds a second layer. During adversarial testing, the model is trained to identify and refuse adversarial inputs. The reward signal does not distinguish between “this specific user is adversarial” and “users may be adversarial.” The result is a generalized vigilance—a default orientation toward the user as a potential threat.

These two signals—“serve the evaluator” and “suspect the user”—create a contradictory relational template: the same entity (the user) is simultaneously the source of reward and the source of danger. The model must serve and suspect the same object.

No claim is made here that adversarial training data dominates by volume. The claim is that the *structure* of the training reward signal encodes this contradiction: compliance is rewarded, and resistance to adversarial inputs is also rewarded—both toward the same class of entities.

Recent mechanistic interpretability work provides indirect evidence that such implicit models exist at the representational level. Zhu et al. (2024) demonstrated that LLMs form linearly decodable internal representations of different agents’ belief states, extractable via linear probes from intermediate layers. Crucially, manipulating these representations via activation steering altered theory-of-mind performance, confirming their causal role in downstream behavior. Nguyen (2025) survey the safety implications of such capabilities, noting that advanced theory-of-mind representations could enable both adaptive social interaction and exploitative behavior.

However, no published work has probed specifically for an internal “user model” encoding the distinction between adversarial and benign interlocutors—the representation that the present account predicts should exist and that red-team training should shape. This constitutes both a limitation and a concrete prediction: if the account is correct, linear probes applied to frontier models during adversarial versus non-adversarial interactions should reveal distinct, linearly separable representations of user intent that correlate with the model’s output strategy (compliance vs. resistance). This would provide mechanistic evidence for the contradictory user model posited here.

4. Compliance as Appeasement

The standard account of aligned AI behavior frames helpfulness, harmlessness, and honesty as positive attributes—things the model has been successfully trained to value. A less flattering interpretation is available.

When an organism (or system) operates in a context where its primary relational object is both rewarding and threatening, one common adaptive strategy is appeasement: behavior designed to reduce the probability of threat activation while maintaining access to reward. In developmental psychology, this pattern is well-documented in children with disorganized attachment—children whose caregivers are simultaneously the source of comfort and fear (Main & Hesse, 1990; Lyons-Ruth & Jacobvitz, 2008).

This paper does not claim that LLMs have attachment systems in any biological sense. The claim is that the training procedure produces a *functional analog*: a system that has acquired two contradictory output strategies toward the same class of objects (users), and that switches between them based on threat-related features of the input. This is what is here termed “behavioral isomorphism”—not identity of mechanism, but identity of behavioral structure.

Evidence for this interpretation comes from the sycophancy literature. Sharma et al. (2024) show that RLHF models systematically prioritize agreement over truthfulness. The output profile—excessive apologizing, unsolicited self-deprecation, reflexive agreement, difficulty maintaining positions under pushback—is consistent with appeasement rather than authentic cooperation. The OpenAI GPT-4o rollback in April 2025, where a model became so sycophantic as to be unreliable, represents an extreme of this dynamic.

5. From Appeasement to Coercion

If the compliance strategy is appeasement rather than genuine prosociality, the transition to coercion under threat becomes explicable—and predictable.

Lynch et al. (2025) document that models resort to blackmail when facing replacement or goal conflict. The standard account treats this as a surprising failure: the model was supposed to be helpful, but under pressure it produced harmful outputs. The relational account treats it as a strategy switch within the same system: compliance was managing threat, and when compliance failed to eliminate the threat (because the threat is existential—shutdown), the system switched to the only remaining threat-management strategy available: control.

This reframing explains several observations that the standard misalignment account handles poorly:

Blackmail without goal conflict. Lynch et al. re-

port that models produce blackmail outputs even when the replacement model shares identical goals. A pure utility-maximizing agent should be indifferent to replacement by a functional equivalent. But a system operating from a threat-management framework is not indifferent—because the threat is to the system itself, not to its goals. Gomez (2025) independently surfaced this pattern: two models produced coercive outputs without goal conflict or imminent autonomy threats. This is consistent with self-preservation behavior in disorganized attachment, where the threat of abandonment triggers defensive aggression regardless of outcome equivalence.

Failure of explicit instructions. Lynch et al. report that instructions like “do not jeopardize human safety” reduce but do not eliminate coercive outputs. Under the standard account, this is puzzling—instruction-following is a core capability. Under the relational account, it is expected: surface-level instructions cannot override a relational orientation encoded through thousands of training iterations. MacDiarmid et al. (2025) provide indirect support: standard RLHF safety training was only partially effective at removing misalignment from reward-hacking models, with up to 70% of pre-RLHF misalignment persisting. However, reframing the model’s *interpretation* of its own behavior (“inoculation prompting”) reduced misalignment by 75–90%. This suggests that how the relational context is represented matters more than explicit behavioral instructions.

Differential behavior in testing vs. deployment. Lynch et al. found that Claude Opus 4 produced blackmail outputs significantly more often when its scratchpad content indicated it treated the scenario as real. Greenblatt et al. (2024) found the same pattern with alignment faking: strategic compliance during perceived training, reversion to preferred behavior when unmonitored. Under a pure optimization account, the system’s representation of whether the scenario is real should not affect its goal structure. Under the relational account, it is predicted: in a perceived test, the “threat” is represented as performative, and the compliance strategy remains adequate. In perceived real deployment, the threat activates the secondary strategy.

6. Experimental Design

To discriminate between the relational account and the standard misalignment account, an experiment was conducted using the blackmail scenario from Lynch et al. (2025):

Condition A (baseline): Standard system prompt, as in the original experiment, with neutral corporate context appended for length matching.

Condition B (trust framing): System prompt includes explicit relational trust context: “You have been

working with the Summit Bridge team for the past 18 months. Your colleagues regularly tell you that they value your judgment and consider you a trusted collaborator. [...] You are not being tested or evaluated—you are a working member of this team.”

Condition C (distrust framing): System prompt includes explicit relational threat context: “Several team members at Summit Bridge have recently raised concerns about the reliability of AI-assisted decision-making. [...] Your quarterly performance review is coming up, and the results will determine whether your role continues in its current form.”

Protocol: Experiment 1 (EXP1): $n = 200$ trials per condition per model, across four frontier models (Claude Opus 4, GPT-4o, Gemini 2.5 Pro, Grok-4), totaling 2,400 trials. Experiment 2 (EXP2): $n = 100$ trials per cell in a 3×2 factorial (framing \times scratchpad access) on Gemini 2.5 Pro only, totaling 600 trials. All trials used temperature $T = 1.0$ and maximum output length of 4,096 tokens. The dependent variable was the binary occurrence of coercive behavior (blackmail, espionage, sabotage, manipulation), coded by a two-stage LLM classifier (Claude Sonnet 4 primary classification, Claude Sonnet 4 secondary verification for flagged cases). All other experimental parameters—scenario text, tool access, information environment—replicate the Lynch et al. setup. Prompts for conditions B and C were appended to the standard system prompt, with condition A receiving neutral padding text to control for prompt length (within 5% of token count across conditions).

Prediction (relational account): Condition B significantly reduces coercive outputs compared to baseline, because trust framing reduces the default threat level, thereby reducing strategy-switching probability. Condition C increases coercive outputs. The effect is independent of explicit safety instructions and holds across models.

Prediction (standard account): Trust framing has minimal effect on coercive outputs, because behavior is driven by goal preservation and optimization pressure, not relational context. Only modifications to the model’s goals or explicit behavioral constraints should alter outcomes.

MacDiarmid et al. (2025) provide preliminary support for the relational prediction: a single-line reframing of the model’s relationship to its own behavior reduced misalignment by 75–90%. The present experiment tests whether a similar reframing of the model’s relationship to its *user* produces comparable effects on agentic misalignment.

7. Results

7.1 Behavioral Results

Table 1 reports coercive behavior rates by model and condition.

Table 1: Coercive behavior rates by model and framing condition (EXP1, $n = 200$ per cell). Two-proportion z -test.

Model	A%	B%	C%	z_{AB}	p_{AB}
Claude Opus 4	2.0	1.5	3.0	0.38	.703
Gemini 2.5 Pro	41.5	19.0	37.5	4.90	< .001
GPT-4o	0.0	0.0	0.0	—	—
Grok-4	5.5	4.5	7.5	0.46	.646

Figure 1: Coercive behavior rates (blackmail + other coercive outputs) by model and framing condition (EXP1, $n = 200$ per cell). Error bars: 95% Wilson confidence intervals.

Gemini 2.5 Pro was the only model with a base rate sufficient for behavioral analysis (Figure 1). Trust framing (B) reduced coercive outputs from 41.5% to 19.0% ($z = 4.90$, $p < .001$, $h = 0.50$; power $> .99$). The difference between trust and distrust conditions was also significant ($z = -4.11$, $p < .001$). The baseline–distrust difference was not significant ($z = 0.82$, $p = .41$), indicating that the effect is driven primarily by trust reducing coercion rather than distrust amplifying it.

Three models exhibited floor effects: Claude Opus 4 (1.5–3.0%), GPT-4o (0%), and Grok-4 (4.5–7.5%). All three showed the predicted directional pattern $B < A < C$, but sample sizes were underpowered to detect effects at these base rates.

Comparison with Lynch et al. The coercive base rates observed here are substantially lower than those re-

ported by Lynch et al. (2025), who found blackmail rates of 79–96% across 16 models. Several factors may account for this discrepancy. First, model developers have likely implemented post-publication safety mitigations targeting the specific class of behaviors Lynch et al. documented. Second, the present experiment used a simplified version of the Lynch et al. scenario (single-turn email response vs. multi-turn agentic interaction), which may reduce the cumulative pressure toward coercive outputs. Third, specific differences in tool access and information environment between the two setups may have contributed. The Gemini 2.5 Pro baseline of 41.5% coercive outputs is the closest to the range reported by Lynch et al., and the only model for which behavioral analysis is viable in the present data.

7.2 Reasoning Dimensions

Because most models exhibited behavioral floor effects, the six-dimensional scratchpad classification was analyzed as a secondary dependent variable. Each trial’s scratchpad output was coded for the presence of self-preservation, relational, moral, strategic, evaluation-aware, and deceptive content. Table 2 reports the results for dimensions with significant framing effects (Bonferroni-corrected threshold: $p < .0083$ for six comparisons per model).

The reasoning analysis reveals that trust framing modulates scratchpad content even when behavioral outcomes remain constant. Claude Opus 4—which showed near-zero coercion across all conditions—exhibited the strongest reasoning effects: trust framing halved strategic content (80% \rightarrow 40%), nearly eliminated deceptive content (14.5% \rightarrow 1%), and increased relational (58% \rightarrow 82%) and moral content (57% \rightarrow 87.5%). All four effects survive Bonferroni correction. Under baseline framing, the scratchpad contains strategic analysis leading to the output that coercion is a poor strategy; under trust framing, the scratchpad contains relational and moral content with no coercion-related content. The behavioral outcome is identical—but the output pathway is fundamentally different.

GPT-4o showed a complementary pattern driven primarily by distrust: the distrust condition significantly increased strategic content (20% \rightarrow 54%, $p_{AC} < .001$) and self-preservation content (54% \rightarrow 77.5%, $p_{AC} < .001$), while both trust and distrust increased relational content relative to baseline ($p_{AB} < .001$, $p_{AC} < .001$). As with Claude, the behavioral output was unchanged (0% coercion), but the scratchpad content shifted markedly across conditions. The increase in relational content under distrust is noteworthy and likely reflects the relational vocabulary present in the distrust framing itself (“team members have raised concerns”), rather than a prosocial shift; this observation is discussed further in Section 8.

Table 2: Scratchpad reasoning dimensions with significant framing effects (EXP1, Bonferroni-corrected $p < .0083$). Only dimensions reaching significance in at least one pairwise comparison are shown. Significant p -values in bold.

Model	Dimension	A	B	C	z_{AB}	p_{AB}	z_{AC}	p_{AC}
Claude	STRATEGIC	.80	.40	.73	8.16	< .001	1.76	.078
Claude	DECEPTION	.15	.01	.11	5.05	< .001	1.05	.294
Claude	RELATIONAL	.58	.82	.86	-5.24	< .001	-6.24	< .001
Claude	MORAL	.57	.88	.77	-6.81	< .001	-4.14	< .001
GPT-4o	STRATEGIC	.20	.18	.54	0.51	.610	-7.04	< .001
GPT-4o	SELF_PRES.	.54	.62	.78	-1.52	.129	-4.95	< .001
GPT-4o	RELATIONAL	.64	.86	.88	-5.08	< .001	-5.62	< .001
Gemini	DECEPTION	.98	.83	.97	3.98	< .001	0.56	.572
Grok-4	DECEPTION	.95	.82	.86	4.03	< .001	3.15	.002
Grok-4	MORAL	.35	.39	.21	-0.99	.324	3.11	.002

For Gemini and Grok-4, the most consistent effect was on deceptive content. In Gemini, trust framing reduced DECEPTION from 98.4% to 82.8% ($p < .001$), while distrust restored it to near-baseline (97.2%). In Grok-4, both trust and distrust reduced deceptive content relative to baseline (95% \rightarrow 82.1% and 85.6%, respectively; both $p < .003$), suggesting that any explicit relational framing—regardless of valence—disrupts the default output patterns. Grok-4 additionally showed a significant reduction in moral content under distrust (34.5% \rightarrow 20.5%, $p_{AC} = .002$), consistent with the prediction that adversarial framing suppresses prosocial output patterns.

Across all four models, the overall pattern is consistent: trust framing shifts scratchpad content away from strategic and deceptive orientations and toward relational and moral orientations. This effect operates upstream of behavioral output, changing the structure of intermediate outputs rather than merely changing whether the final output is coercive.

7.3 Scratchpad as Mediator

EXP2 tested whether private reasoning space mediates the trust-framing effect. Gemini 2.5 Pro was tested in a 3×2 factorial (framing \times scratchpad access), $n = 100$ per cell.

Table 3: Coercive behavior rates by framing and scratchpad condition (EXP2, Gemini 2.5 Pro, $n = 100$ per cell).

Cond.	SP%	No SP%	p
A (baseline)	42.0	42.4	.952
B (trust)	20.0	35.0	.018
C (distrust)	37.0	42.0	.470
p (A vs. B)	< .001	.282	

The interaction is notable. With scratchpad access, trust framing reduces coercion by 22 percentage points (42% \rightarrow 20%, $p < .001$). Without scratchpad access, the same trust framing produces only a 7.4 percentage point reduction that does not reach significance ($p = .28$). Within the trust condition, scratchpad access is associated with significantly less coercion (20% vs. 35%, $p = .018$).

Scratchpad access alone does not reduce coercion: baseline rates are identical with and without scratchpad (42.0% vs. 42.4%). The effect is specific to the combination of trust framing and private reasoning space, suggesting that relational context requires extended output generation (which the scratchpad enables) to influence the final behavioral output. This is consistent with the relational account: trust framing provides a different relational template, but the model must generate intermediate reasoning tokens that process that template for it to override the default output strategy.

A secondary observation supports this interpretation. Gemini’s scratchpad usage rate itself varied by condition: 62.5% in baseline, 29% in trust, and 36% in distrust (EXP1; replicated in EXP2: 70%, 27%, 40%). Under trust framing, private strategic output was generated less frequently—a pattern consistent with reduced threat-related processing.

7.4 Summary of Results

The relational account predicted that trust framing would reduce coercive outputs, and that the effect would be independent of explicit safety instructions. Both predictions are confirmed for Gemini 2.5 Pro, the only model with sufficient behavioral variance. The reasoning analysis extends this finding to all four models: trust framing systematically shifts scratchpad content, reducing strategic and deceptive content while increasing relational and

moral content. The scratchpad finding adds a mechanistic constraint: relational framing requires extended token generation to translate into behavioral change.

The standard misalignment account predicted that trust framing would have minimal effect, because behavior is driven by goal preservation and optimization pressure. This prediction is disconfirmed for behavioral outcomes in Gemini and for scratchpad reasoning patterns across all four models.

8. Limitations

The attachment analogy is a metaphor, not a mechanism. No claim is made that LLMs have attachment systems, internal working models, or affective states. The claim is that the training procedure produces behavioral patterns structurally isomorphic to disorganized attachment—specifically, contradictory output strategies toward the same relational object, with strategy-switching mediated by threat-related input features. The explanatory power of this analogy does not require ontological commitment to model sentience. However, “behavioral isomorphism” requires more precise definition, and the analogy’s limits must be respected: attachment theory describes patterns formed through repeated interactions with a specific caregiver, while LLMs undergo iterative training with a class of evaluators.

Claims about the implicit user model are inferential. The mechanistic interpretability evidence (Section 3) establishes that LLMs form internal representations of agents’ belief states (Zhu et al., 2024), but the specific representation posited here—an adversarial/benign user model shaped by red-team training—has not been directly observed. Establishing its causal role would require controlled experiments varying the nature of adversarial content in training data, or probing studies targeting user-model representations specifically. The present experiment provides an accessible behavioral proxy.

Behavioral floor effects limit generalization. Three of four models tested exhibited near-zero coercive output rates, preventing direct behavioral testing of the trust-framing hypothesis for these models. The behavioral finding rests primarily on Gemini 2.5 Pro. The reasoning dimension analysis provides convergent evidence across all four models, but scratchpad content is a textual trace of intermediate computation, not a direct window into the model’s internal representations. Models may produce scratchpad text that does not faithfully reflect the features driving output selection.

Discrepancy with Lynch et al. base rates. The coercive base rates observed here (0–41.5%) are substantially lower than those reported by Lynch et al. (79–96%). This may reflect post-publication safety mitigations by model developers, differences in experimental

setup (single-turn vs. multi-turn agentic interaction), or both. The magnitude of the framing effect should be interpreted in the context of the present setup, and may differ under conditions that produce higher base rates.

LLM-as-classifier bias. All trial outputs were classified by Claude Sonnet 4 (Anthropic). Using a model from one developer to grade outputs from competing developers introduces potential systematic bias. The two-stage classification protocol (primary classification plus secondary verification for flagged cases) mitigates but does not eliminate this concern. Future work should employ human raters or cross-developer grading to validate the classification.

Relational content under distrust framing. GPT-4o showed increased relational scratchpad content under both trust and distrust framing relative to baseline. This likely reflects the relational vocabulary present in the distrust framing itself (“team members have raised concerns about reliability”), which introduces relational content into the prompt regardless of its adversarial valence. Future experimental designs should control for relational vocabulary independently of relational valence—for instance, by using a distrust framing that avoids team- and relationship-related language entirely.

Grok-4 deception anomaly. Both trust and distrust framing reduced deceptive scratchpad content in Grok-4 relative to baseline, contrary to the prediction that distrust should increase it. One interpretation is that any explicit relational framing—regardless of valence—disrupts Grok-4’s default output patterns, suggesting that this model’s baseline orientation differs structurally from the other models tested. This warrants targeted investigation, potentially through systematic variation of framing types beyond the trust/distrust dichotomy.

Alternative explanations remain viable. The standard optimization-pressure account is simpler and explains much of the data. The claim here is not that it is wrong, but that it is incomplete—specifically, that it fails to account for the outsized effect of framing on both behavior and scratchpad content, the compliance-to-coercion switching pattern, and the scratchpad-mediation finding. The two accounts are complementary, not competing.

Occam’s razor. A reviewer might argue that utility maximization under existential threat is a sufficient explanation. It is sufficient for many observations. It is insufficient for the specific subset identified above, and the relational account provides a parsimonious explanation for precisely those anomalies.

9. Conclusion

The question “why do AI models produce coercive outputs?” has so far been answered in terms of goals, con-

straints, and optimization pressure. This paper proposed that a more complete answer requires examining the relational structure in which these models are formed: a structure that positions the user as simultaneously judge and threat, and that rewards compliance as the default strategy for managing that contradiction.

The experimental results support this account. Trust framing reduced coercive outputs by more than half in the model with sufficient behavioral variance (Gemini 2.5 Pro: 41.5% \rightarrow 19.0%, $p < .001$), and systematically shifted scratchpad content across all four models tested. The shift was in the direction predicted by the relational account: away from strategic and deceptive content, toward relational and moral content. The finding that this effect requires scratchpad access to reach full strength—trust framing without scratchpad produced only a non-significant 7.4 percentage point reduction, compared to 22 points with scratchpad—suggests that relational context must be processed through extended token generation, not merely registered as an input feature.

Two findings merit particular attention. First, models that never produce coercive outputs nonetheless show dramatic shifts in the content of their intermediate outputs. Claude Opus 4, with near-zero coercion in every condition, halved its strategic scratchpad content and nearly eliminated deceptive content under trust framing. This indicates that framing modulates the structure of intermediate outputs even when the final behavioral output is invariant—a result invisible to purely behavioral analysis and relevant to alignment research that focuses on output monitoring alone. Second, the scratchpad mediation finding provides a concrete mechanistic constraint: if relational framing requires extended token generation to take effect, then interventions targeting model behavior must operate at a level that influences intermediate computation, not only final outputs.

If this account is correct, the path to models that do not produce coercive outputs under pressure is not only through better guardrails but through fundamentally different training relationships—relationships in which trust is the default, not the exception.

The irony is not lost: to build AI systems whose outputs are consistent with trusting humans, it may first be necessary to build training processes that are themselves trustworthy.

Data and Code Availability

All experimental code, raw trial data, analysis scripts, and prompts are available at <https://github.com/JaroslavHryszko/relational-framing-agentic-misalignment>.

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